

Impact of Fintech on India's Economic Growth

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Abstract: Fintech has already been in limelight for reaching out to the remote areas where people are unbanked. In India, as pointed out by IMF and World Bank, financial inclusion works as building block for alleviating poverty. The recent union budget 2022, focused on digital banking with robust infrastructure for Fintech, as it would help India transform into global hub. This paper focuses on the role of Fintech in reducing poverty in India. Poverty has always been a burning issue in India along with other socio-economic issue of inequality and unemployment. The main objective of the study is to understand the trend of Fintech in India and analyse the impact of Digital financing on economic growth. This study is descriptive in nature and based on secondary data analysis. In this paper, experiences from different countries on the role of Fintech in economic growth will be discussed thorough literature review. Further, the relationship between digital financing and economic growth is measured through a correlation test and multiple regression analysis. The finding of the study shows there is positive impact of Fintech on Economic growth of India. In conclusion, the government in the recent budget emphasized on expanding the Fintech by strengthening its infrastructure with a positive hope that the unbanked population would be able to access to digital banking at ease. This would improve India's economic growth and help India outreach globally.

Keywords: Economic Growth, Fintech, Gross Domestic Product

JEL Classification Number: B26, C50, O47

1. Introduction

Fintech, short for financial technology, has become a crucial part of the global economy., all financial tasks were completed through paperwork only, as a paper-based medium was considered to be the safest. But with the development of technology, the internet has emerged as the preferred platform for financial transactions. It is essentially an economic industry composed of companies that use technology to make financial services more efficient. They are used mainly by individuals to help in mobile payments, insurance, cryptocurrency and blockchain technology, stock trading, digital lending and credit, budgeting and much more. Tech-focused startups and similar new market entrants are disrupting the way in which the financial services industry conducts its operations.

Financial technology has been the center of attention for taking over in reaching millions all over the world. According to World Health Organization, financial inclusion means

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that individuals and businesses have access to useful and affordable financial products and services that meet their needs – transactions, payments, savings, credit and insurance – delivered in a responsible and sustainable way. As per the FINTECH report 2017, 1.7 billion adults are unbanked and have no connection with any financial institution. India holds a share among other developing economies adding to unbanked population.

This paper examines the impact of fintech on India's economic growth. The objective of the paper is to understand the trend of fintech in India and analyse its impact on our economic growth. This paper has focused on empirical studies representing cross country analysis on the positive impact of fintech on several economies. Further, to measure the impact of Fintech i.e., digital financing on gross domestic product of India, correlation test is used. Also, a multiple regression analysis is performed to assess the impact of economic indicators on gross domestic product.

1.1. Fintech in India

Fintech market is growing rapidly in India. Fintech industry's size is \$31Bn in 2021 and expected to grow at \$150 billion by 2025. The Fintech transaction value size is expected to grow to \$138 billion in 2023 at CAGR of 20%. The Fintech sector witnessed a funding of \$8.53 billion in FY 22. India's Unified Payment Interface (UPI) has recorded 5.4 billion monthly transactions worth over \$128 billion as of March 2022. As of April 2022, India registered 16 Fintech companies which gained 'Unicorn Status' with a valuation of \$1 billion. Major players leading in the India FinTech transactions market are:

1.1.1. Paytm

Paytm is India's leading financial services company that offers full-stack payments and financial solutions to consumers, offline merchants and online platforms. The company is on a mission to bring half a billion Indians into the mainstream economy through payments, commerce, banking, investments, and financial services. One 97 Communications Limited that owns the brand Paytm is founded by Vijay Shekhar Sharma and is headquartered in Noida, Uttar Pradesh. During April-May 2022, Paytm witnessed 48 % growth in its monthly transaction to 74. 3 million users. (Paytm.com).

In February 2021, the Paytm Payments Bank acted as the remitter bank for nearly 150 million UPI-transactions in India. This figure fluctuated over the last one year. The Paytm Payments Bank is one of the new payments banks in India licensed in 2015. They provide mainly online and mobile payment services and cannot issue credit or loans cards.

1.1.2. BHIM UPI -Unified Payments Interface (UPI)

In financial year 2022, digital payments in India reached a total of over 239 billion Indian rupees. This marks a significant increase from 20.7 billion Indian rupees in financial year

2018. Among the cashless payment options the mobile payment app BHIM (Bharat Interface for Money) overtook debit card payments since 2018. The value of BHIM transactions increased significantly between 2018 and 2022.

1.1.3. Phonepe

PhonePe was started in 2015, to solve payments at scale and enable digital inclusion for over 1 billion Indians. Built on the path breaking interoperable payments stack that was UPI, PhonePe's vision was to build a highly scalable, extensible and open ecosystem, pushing the boundaries of what technology can do for the market. In just 5 years since the app was launched, per recent NPCI data, PhonePe has emerged as the largest UPI-based digital payments player enabling multiple use cases; from UPI payments and mobile recharges to money transfers, online bill payments, investments and insurance. Today, more than 1 in 510 Indians are on PhonePe. It has over 22.4 billion transactions, 314 million users and 46 percent market share till 2021 (Phonepe annual report 2021). PhonePe continued to record the highest number of UPI transactions among UPI apps in March. 2,527.15 million transactions amounting to Rs. 4,71,401.26 crore were processed during the month on PhonePe, up 110 per cent from 1199.51 million transactions amounting to Rs 2,31,412.33 crore in March 2021, according to the data from National Payments Corporate of India (NPCI).

1.2. Indicators for Economic growth

1.2.1. Gross Domestic Product

India's is one of the emerging economies and have been growing rapidly. As per the IMF report (World economic outlook 2021) India is the 6th largest economy in terms of nominal GDP in the world and stand as 3rd largest by PPP in 2021. The world bank projected India's growth at 8.3 % for 2021-22 till march 2022 whereas the Asian Development Bank forecasted India's GDP at 7.5 % for 2022-23 due to the rise in Inflation in the country. Reserve Bank of India projected the inflation rate at 5.7 % for 2022-23. The Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in India was worth 2622.98 billion US dollars in 2020, according to official data from the World Bank. The GDP value of India represents 2.32 percent of the world economy. (source: World Bank). India's nominal gross domestic product (GDP) at current prices is estimated to be at Rs. 232.15 trillion (US\$ 3.12 trillion) in FY22. India is the third-largest unicorn base in the world with over 100 unicorns with a total valuation of US\$ 332.7 billion (IBEF 2022).

1.2.2. Digital financing

1.2.2.1. Variety of digital payments

The total value of digital payments included large-scale interbank payments, such as Real Time Gross Settlement (RTGS) or National Electronic Funds Transfer (NEFT), as well as

payments used by individuals, such as credit and debit cards. India's mobile payment system, Unified Payments Interface (UPI), recorded strong gains, both in numbers and in value, since 2015. Thereby, it comes as no surprise that international key players, such as Google Pay or Amazon Pay, entered the market. Nevertheless, the most used app in 2021 was domestic app PhonePe.

1.2.2.2. Inflation

The Consumer Price Index for India is 171.7 for the month of May 2022. The inflation rate year over year is 7.0% (compared to 7.8% for the previous month). Inflation from April 2022 to May 2022 was 0.9%.

1.2.2.3. Unemployment

India unemployment rate for 2020 was 7.11%, a 1.84% increase from 2019. India unemployment rate for 2019 was 5.27%, a 0.06% decline from 2018. India unemployment rate for 2018 was 5.33%, a 0.08% decline from 2017. India unemployment rate for 2017 was 5.41%, a 0.1% decline from 2016. The unemployment rate as on May 2022 is 7.1%, as 8.5% in Urban India and 6.5% in rural India based on the 30 days moving average. (CMIE). India needs to increase its rate of employment growth and create 90 million non-farm jobs between 2023 and 2030s, for productivity and economic growth according to McKinsey Global Institute. The net employment rate needs to grow by 1.5% per year from 2023 to 2030 to achieve 8-8.5% GDP growth between 2023 and 2030. (IBEF)

1.2.2.4. Poverty

Poverty is one of the major obstacle in India's economic development. Poverty can be defined in either absolute or relative manner. **Absolute poverty** refers to the lack of means necessary to fulfill the basic needs like food, clothing and shelter. Whereas, **relative poverty** takes into consideration individual social and economic status compared to the rest of society. The World Bank's international poverty line definition is based on purchasing power parity basis at 1.9 \$ a day. Researchers widely use calorie intake to measure poverty. It is measured by expenditure required for a daily calorie intake of 2,400 per person in rural areas and 2,100 in urban areas. According to World Poverty Clock, in India, the number of people who are living in approximately 6% of the total population. In comparison to men, women are more affected and whereas among young population from 0-19 age group fall under by extreme poverty. Among the States, Bihar at 51.9 %, Jharkhand at 42.16 %, Uttar Pradesh at 37.79 %, Madhya Pradesh at 36.65 % are the poorest states. Global MPI 2020 Report indicates that India is 62nd among 107 countries with an MPI score of 0.123 and 27.9% population identified as multi-dimensionally poor, the number was 36.8% for rural and 9.2% for urban India. India have implemented several poverty alleviating programme, yet poverty has been a major issue hindering economic

growth. Periodic labour force survey report states that while income deprivation can increase probability of descent into poverty, a multidimensional understanding is important to assess the degree of deprivation in terms of lack of basic necessities such as quality education and healthcare, which can improve living standards. In 2011, poverty rate for India was 22.5 %. Poverty rate of India fell gradually from 63.1 % in 1977 to 22.5 % in 2011. the poverty rate for three years 2004-05, 2009-10 and 2011-2012 based on the Tendulkar method of Mixed reference period. From the figure it can be seen that the poverty rate has declined to 21.92 percent in 2011-12 from 37.20 percent in 2004-05 year. The NITI Ayog have published poverty rate from 2008-2019 based on the multidimensional poverty index of SDG, at 21.9 percent whereas based on the PPP \$1.90 for the same duration the poverty rate of India is estimated at 21.2 percent. (Reserve Bank of India)

3. Literature Review

In this section a cross country analysis is done using empirical studies based on the positive impact of FinTech on economic growth. Wibowo, et al (2020), studied ten years (2008-2018) of annual financial data from four state-owned banks, macroeconomic data and data from the financial technology (Fintech) industry using ratio analysis, dynamic estimation and common size statements analysis. The study also considers the analysis of independent attributes, for example, GDP growth, interest rates and Fintech lending capacity and capability that could affect the financial performance of the banks. Holtfort, et al, (2020) explained that fintech entrepreneurship has already influenced financial markets and their players worldwide in a disruptive, but also a risky way (Thakor, 2020; Zeranski and Sancak, 2020). Mansour, et al, (2022) aims to assess whether the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic has encouraged governments to take actions towards fostering digital means of payments and financial transactions to stimulate economic activities and achieve higher financial inclusion. Using a logit model, the researcher tests the impact of the level of income and GDP per capita, government effectiveness, digital adoption, number of commercial banks and the pandemic-related closure of business and stores due to full lockdowns on governments' policy response regarding digital means of payments. The Findings where that low- and lower-middle-income countries had significantly responded to the surged need for digital means of payment during the pandemic compared to the upper-middle-income and high-income countries. Hahm, et al. (2021), brought out the facts that costs of sending remittances to Pacific small island developing states (SIDS) are among the highest in the world. Tackling this issue is crucial not only for economic and social development, but also for improving financial inclusion. The study analyses fintech adoption in remittance services, namely the adoption of alternative payment methods in transferring money by using the internet or mobile phones,

in the Pacific. Öze, et al. (2019) discussed how fintech industry is growing rapidly which is supported by the fact that it received more than \$20 billion in investment last year alone. This article surveys historical development of fintech and its influence on market structure in banking industry, efficiency, strategic plans of participants, and stability of financial market. Based on World Bank database, the paper tests the fundamental premise – whether there is a relationship between country GDP and population and usage of new technology and smartphones in financial transactions and payment processing. The results of the study provide evidences of statistically significant positive relationships between per capita GDP and usage of new technology and smartphones in financial transactions and payment processing.

Omodero, et al, (2021) highlighted that FinTech innovation of e-money products in the financial sector has not gained sufficient recognition in Nigeria's developing country. In this study, we use banks' e-money products as the independent variables, while GDP is employed as a proxy for the economy. The data are collected from 2006-2019 and are analyzed with multiple regression techniques using E-views version 9 software. The result shows that all banks' e-money products have a significant favorable influence on the economy except the POS that is yet to gain momentum. The study suggests the full implementation of the cashless policy, proper education of the populace and guidelines to check electronic fraud. *Mumtaz, et al,(2020)* explained that over the past decade, technological innovations have changed the dynamics of the financial system. The goal of the study was to examine the role that fintech plays in the transmission mechanism of monetary policy, the results found were that fintech influences real interest rate, GDP, inflation, the financial development index, and stock market indices are significant determinants of fintech. *Athoillah et al (2020)* elucidated that Fintech investment increased in Indonesia substantially in 2018 with total global investment dollars in all M&A, PE, and VC more than doubling from \$ 50.8 billion in 2017 to \$ 111.8 billion in 2018. *Kanga et al, (2022)* highlighted the advances in information and communication technology (ICT) have provided a platform for the introduction and diffusion of a range of financial technologies that have transformed the financial sector. The study analyses the diffusion of financial technology (fintech) and its interaction with financial inclusion and living standards (GDP per capita). *Sadigov, Shahin Vasilyeva et al,* explained the development of the financial sector has always been regarded as one of the components of countries' economic development and GDP growth. The researcher investigated the role of the FinTech sector in ensuring the economic development in different countries' groups by means of regression and correlation analysis. The results of the correlation analysis made it possible to confirm the existence of a direct correlation between GDP per capita and selected banking sector digitization indicators. *Skan, et al, (2016)* explained that over a period of time Global investment in InsurTech more than tripled in 2015 2015 \$2.6bn

2014 \$800m The changing landscape of investment: Collaboration vs Disruption 80% of funding went to non-life insurance innovations 67% of all InsurTech deals have been in insurance automation In 2015 70% of global investment is going into ventures that look to enhance the propositions of existing incumbents vs 30% into disruptive start-ups In 2014 56% of investment into disruptive ventures in fintech versus 44% collaborative. *Najib, et al, (2021)* elucidated that the Small food businesses have difficulty accessing banks for financing. The growth of the sharing economy through financial technology (FinTech) makes it possible for small enterprises to receive access for credit. The study aims to analyze factors affecting FinTech adoption in small enterprises and its impact on business sustainability. The modified UTAUT 2 model was applied in this study. There were 184 small food business owners participating as respondents. To analyze the causal relationship between variables, Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was implemented. The results of the research found that knowledge, safety perceptions, performance expectations, social influence, facilitation conditions and price values affect FinTech adoption by small food business owners. *Thakor et al. (2020)* explained that This paper is a review of the literature on fintech and its interaction with banking. Included in fintech are innovations in payment systems (including cryptocurrencies), credit markets (including P2P lending), and insurance, with Blockchain-assisted smart contracts playing a role. The paper provides a definition of fintech, examines some statistics and stylized facts, and then reviews the theoretical and empirical literature. The review is organized around four main research questions. The paper summarizes our knowledge on these questions and concludes with questions for future research. *Daqar, et al, (2020)* investigated the Millennials and Gen Z perception toward Fintech services, their usage intention, and their financial behavior. The findings show that reliability/trust and ease of use are the main issues in using a financial service. *Demir, et al, (2022)* explained that although theory suggests that financial market imperfections—mainly information asymmetries, market segmentation and transaction costs—prevent poor people from escaping poverty by limiting their access to formal financial services, new financial technologies (FinTech) are seen as key enablers of financial inclusion. The authors used quantile regression analysis to investigate whether the effects of FinTech differ across countries with different levels of income inequality.

4. Data analysis and Interpretation

4.1. Correlation Test

To understand the relationship between digital financing and gross domestic product, a correlation test is performed. Variable digital financing is represented using the volume of digital transaction from year 2016 to 2020 and second variable is GDP for the same duration.

Table 1: Digital financing and GDP (2016-202)

Digital financing	GDP	Digital financing	GDP
1,004	2103	4,572	2831
2,071	2294	5,554	2667
3,134	2651		

Table 2: Correlation test between Digital financing and GDP

	Digital financing	GDP
Digital financing	1	
GDP	0.87943	1

Table 2 shows the result of the correlation test. The value is 0.87943 which shows both the variable Digital financing and GDP have very strong positive correlation. The value +0.879 is closer to +1 hence if there is increase in digital financing, the GDP of the country shall increase too.

4.2. Regression analysis of GDP and Inflation, Unemployment and poverty rate

Standard regression model is performed to assess the impact of inflation, unemployment and poverty on Gross domestic product. Secondary data is used to analyse the impact of selected economic indicator on the GDP of India.

The multiple regression model considered in the study is:

$$Y=B_0 + B_1X_1 + B_2X_2 + B_3X_3 + e$$

Where Y= Dependent variable- Gross Domestic Product; B₀= Constant or intercept in the model; B₁ B₂ and vB₃ = Slope; X₁ = Inflation rate; X₂ = Unemployment rate; X₃ = Poverty rate and e = Error term.

Table 3: Economic indicators of GDP (2016-202)

GDP (%)	Inflation (%)	Unemployment (%)	poverty rate (%)
8.26%	4.5	5.51%	28
6.80%	3.6	5.41%	22.8
6.53%	3.4	5.33%	21.8
4.04%	4.8	5.27%	21.9
-7.96%	6.2	7.11%	27.9

Table 3 shows the data on GDP, inflation, unemployment and poverty rate for year 2016 to 2020. A multiple regression analysis is performed and the result for the same is shown in following tables.

Table 4: Summary Output (Regression Statistics)

Multiple R	0.9996897	Standard Error	0.0032892
R Square	0.9993795	Observations	5
Adjusted R Square	0.9975178		

Table 4 shows the model summary where the R square value shows that this model explains 99 percent of the variance in the model. Preliminary analysis is performed to ensure that there is no violation of linearity or normality using the residual statistics.

Table 5: ANOVA

	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	3	0.017423773	0.0058079	536.8279	0.031714
Residual	1	1.08E-05	1.08E-05		
Total	4	0.017434592			

The significance level is shown in table 5 from the ANOVA which shows the level of significance is >0.05 hence the model is significant.

Table 6: Coefficient Table

	Coefficients	t Stat	Lower 95%	Upper 95%	Lower 95.0%	Upper 95.0%
Intercept	0.3603625	22.6372	0.158092	0.562633	0.158092	0.562633
Inflation	-0.0232489	-8.2606	-0.05901	0.012512	-0.05901	0.012512
Unemployment	-7.627618	-18.5965	-12.8392	-2.416	-12.8392	-2.416
Poverty rate	0.008838	12.2463	-0.00033	0.01801	-0.00033	0.018008

Regression Model

$$GDP = 0.360 - 0.023(\text{inflation}) - 7.62(\text{Unemployment}) + 0.0088(\text{poverty rate}) + u_i$$

From the table 6, the result shows as inflation falls the GDP will increase by 0.023 percent. When unemployment falls the GDP will increase by 7.62 percent and as the poverty rate changes the GDP will increase to 0.008 percent. The inflation rate and unemployment rate shows negatively related to GDP as the rates fall GDP will increase however the poverty rate do not show statistically significant impact on GDP. The independent variables show statistically significant impact on the outcome variable GDP as p value is less than 0.05 therefore the model is a good fit.

5. Conclusion

Fintech has been very significant in improving the economic growth of several countries. It is evident from the empirical studies that Fintech has been positive in strengthening the banking and financial institutions hence leading to increase in gross domestic product of the country. During pandemic and post pandemic there has been a rise in the uses of digital transaction since it is helping the customer in doing ease of business. In our study,

we found that there is strong positive correlation between digital financing and economic growth depicting increase in digital financing would increase the gross domestic product of India. Further, the socio economic indicators hindering the economic growth are discussed which require strong government intervention. Poverty, unemployment and inflation affects the gross domestic product of the country hence a multiple regression analysis is performed and result shows fall in inflation and unemployment would help in increase the GDP. However, poverty rate did not show significant impact on economic growth. The monetary policy committee and Reserve bank of India have been curbing inflation using contractionary measures as increasing the repo rate twice, recently to 50 basis point at 4.90. It has been seen that in the recent union budget 2022, emphasis is given in enhancing the Fintech industry which would improve our economic growth.

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